

AUDIT OF FINANCIAL STATEMENTS AS A TOOL IN MUNICIPAL WASTE MANAGEMENT

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The article examines the relevance and significance of financial statement auditing in the municipal waste management system in the context of urban infrastructure development and addressing global environmental challenges. The insufficient development of financial statement audit methodologies in international practice for organizations involved in municipal waste processing indicates the need for its advancement taking into account the industry-specific characteristics of these organizations' activities. The authors highlight the advantages of a scientifically based audit methodology, which will allow, on the one hand, to organize the audit engagement more rationally in accordance with the disaggregation of financial statement indicators; on the other hand, to identify new audit objects for organizations engaged in municipal waste disposal and biogas extraction at landfills, namely: "Municipal Waste Biomass," "Renewable Energy Resource Reserves," and "Attracted Natural Capital." These objects distinctly influence the materiality of financial statement indicators, the risks of misstatement, and the list of substantive audit procedures.

Keywords: financial statements, audit methodology, audit procedures, risks of misstatement, materiality level, disaggregation of financial statement items, municipal waste management.

The acute problem of municipal waste disposal is linked to the global scale of its generation. According to international experts, about 1.3 billion tons of municipal solid waste are collected annually worldwide [1]. Today, waste poses a threat to environmental safety and human health.

The necessity of solving the waste disposal problem in international practice, including municipal waste, has led to the emergence of an independent field – «waste management» – aimed at regulating and developing methods for organizing waste collection, transportation, processing (utilization), incineration, and disposal. The presence in each country of well-developed theoretical and methodological foundations for forming a municipal waste management system indicates the relevance of developing the corresponding infrastructure in cities (regions) to improve the quality of life of the population and prevent environmental damage. Currently, global experience shows that significant progress has been made in this direction: waste processing and incineration plants have been built, environmentally equipped landfills and waste sorting facilities have been created, and waste transportation logistics routes have been established. Various approaches to the utilization of municipal waste are applied, the main ones being: recycling – the return of individual components of solid municipal waste to economic circulation (e.g., paper, plastic, textiles, glass, and others); composting – the use of the organic part of solid municipal waste in the production of soil and mineral fertilizers; incineration – the use of waste to generate heat and/or electrical energy; and biogas extraction at disposal sites for the purpose of generating electrical energy.

However, the practical implementation of waste utilization methods requires significant capital investment. For this reason, some countries have less developed infrastructures for municipal waste management, while others have more developed ones. For instance, leaders in this area are Sweden (recycles 99% of solid municipal waste) and Japan (about 90%) [2]. Housing and communal services enterprises typically strive to develop this area through their own and borrowed funds, government support, international funds, and by attracting other investors.

Consequently, due to the growing need to increase investment in this area, the reliability of accounting information and financial statement indicators of organizations utilizing municipal waste is a significant aspect of the activities of organizations within the municipal waste

management system, including organizations engaged in municipal waste disposal and biogas extraction at disposal sites.

Transparent and reliable information support for such activities contributes not only to making well-founded decisions in the field of waste management but also to the investment attractiveness of organizations within the municipal waste management system. The availability of audit opinions containing a reliable opinion, as well as detailed written information, facilitates the attraction of external financing and increases investor interest in the economic entity. A high-quality audit and a positive audit opinion can increase confidence in the company's activities. Investors, local authorities, partners, and clients will interact more actively with an organization whose data and indicators they can trust. Moreover, auditors can optimize waste management processes at all stages of their life cycle and improve financial performance through the timely detection of accounting errors.

Audit contributes to identifying and eliminating financial and economic activity risks, thereby helping the organization avoid losses. Thus, the audit of financial statements represents a potential tool for addressing issues related to municipal waste management, attracting investment, and developing the infrastructure of the municipal waste management system.

However, to date, there are no clear methodological explanations for auditing the financial statements of organizations in the municipal waste management system, including organizations engaged in municipal waste disposal and biogas extraction at disposal sites, neither in the Republic of Belarus, the Republic of Uzbekistan, nor in other countries worldwide. It should be noted that the International Standards on Auditing and the current National Auditing Rules, approved by the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Belarus, establish general recommendations for organizing, planning, applying audit procedures, and documenting audit results. They do not take into account the specifics of the activities of the entities being audited, which is important when planning, assessing the risks of material misstatement, and conducting the audit engagement.

The methodological support and tools for auditing the financial statement indicators of business entities are based on theoretical principles and methodologies. These include approaches to segmenting financial statements or disaggregating their items, forming audit objects; approaches to determining materiality levels and assessing risks; applying an algorithm of audit procedures; and others.

For instance, the segmentation of financial statement items in auditing has been examined in the works of various domestic and foreign scholars, such as I.N. Bogataya, N.V. Parushina, A.D. Sheremet, V.P. Suits, E.A. Klinova, P.Ya. Papkovskaya, L.V. Masko [3]. The problems of determining materiality levels were addressed in the works of authors V.N. Lemesh, A.R. Lavrinenko [4], K.K. Arabyan, and T. Rybak. The main provisions of risk-oriented auditing methodology were analyzed in the works of S.M. Bychkova, Yu.Yu. Kochineva, and A.V. Petukh. In general, issues of audit theory and practice at various stages of its development have been explored in the foreign works of the founders of auditing, including R. Montgomery, R. Adams, J. Robertson, V. Brink, and others.

Since the activities of organizations within the municipal waste management system are often related to environmental protection activities or the use of natural resources, it is important to note the significance of verifying environmental components within the audit of financial statement indicators. This topic has been addressed in the scientific works of L.V. Masko [3], E.S. Eremeeva, A.V. Zotov, P.Ya. Papkovskaya, and others.

Despite the significant contribution of scholars to the development of methodological support and tools for auditing financial statements, a well-developed and scientifically substantiated approach to auditing the financial statements of organizations in the municipal waste management system is lacking. In particular, there are no recommendations for conducting audits in organizations engaged in municipal waste disposal and biogas extraction at landfills that would account for the specifics of business processes, the corresponding life cycle stages of municipal waste, and the life cycle stages of the landfill. In our view, well-developed methodological support

and tools for auditing the financial statements of organizations managing municipal waste would allow, firstly, for a more rational organization and higher quality of the audit engagement, as well as for the distribution of responsibilities among auditors; and secondly, for the identification of new audit objects such as «municipal waste biomass», «renewable energy resource reserves» (biogas reserves), and «attracted natural capital». These objects have a definite impact on the materiality of financial statement items, misstatement risks, and the list of substantive audit procedures. Previously, we investigated the economic essence of the new accounting objects «municipal waste biomass» and «renewable energy resource reserves» (biogas reserves) for organizations within the municipal waste management system and proposed a methodology for their accounting [5], [6].

Thus, the conducted research indicates that the audit of financial statements can serve as a tool in municipal waste management at the organizational level and within the urban housing and communal services infrastructure. In this regard, we consider it relevant to develop methodological support and tools for auditing the financial statement indicators of municipal organizations engaged in municipal waste disposal and biogas extraction at landfills to conduct high-quality audit engagements.

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